

Research Article

RUDIMENTS OF EXISTENTIALISM

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Abstract

Existentialism is a philosophical theory which emphasizes the existence of an individual as a free being. Twentieth century witnessed emergence of multiple philosophical and literary movements that sought a key to define human existence and meaning in the beginning as a revolt against the existing intensity in political, social, literary, scientific fields. Existentialism stands prominent in literary and social terrains as a philosophical and literary movement connected with human existence, freedom, choice, pursuit of meaning in the absurd world. The domain of existentialism is undoubtedly rooted in the society but it deals with individual subjectively and objectively. The perceptiveness of each philosophical thought appeals in contrast to the ones proposed by ancient philosophers but its origins are examined and explored with reference to responsibility pertaining to an individual and the own involvement in activities as opposed to being governed by universal moral ideologies. Tracking back its logical analysis and evolution from the introspective reflections and inquiries of the ancient Eastern and Western practices to its rebellious expression with resolutions partaking the paradox proposed by Kierkegaard, Nietzsche, Dostoevsky, Beckett, Sartre, Camus, de Beauvoir, Heidegger, Kafka etc. The study unveils the philosophy covering recurring themes anguish, freedom, authenticity, choice, solitude, alienation, mortality to embody the cry of individuals in anguish against imprisoned unavoidable reality in the orderless, meaningless, absurd world.

Keywords: Absurd, Authenticity, Evolution, Existence, Individual, Philosophical.

Introduction

Existentialism is a philosophical theory which highlights the existence of individual as free and responsible agent. The moral contentions of the existing situation of human life raised despair, anguish, solitude, alienation, disillusionment and thrust into prominence at the end of World War II. Existentialism is a philosophy of existence which arrested the attention of famous American writers in New York, in Paris and beyond Europe as well. Marvin Faber has written in his periodical that Heidegger, one created key to unleash the international menace all people. He calls it "the domain of inauthentic". p.1. It is hence, not so easy to define existential philosophy satisfactorily. Existentialism confronts man with a possibility of innumerable of choices, believes Sartre; however, Sartre and Heidegger powerfully affirm that questions concerning this philosophy need to be meditated in solitude and cannot be subjected to discussion or discourse in public, as this philosophy pertains much to individual.

Ideologies of Popular Existential Philosophers

The word 'existence' in its true philosophical sense, is used by Soren Kierkegaard. But Kierkegaard may neither be called as existentialist or philosopher. In fact, he is philosopher with fixed doctrine. To grasp what existentialism proposes, it necessitates to contrast the concept with classical origins of the philosophy proposed by great philosophers like Socrates, Augustine,

Plato, ancient Greek Philosophers, Baruch Spinoza, Dutch-Jewish novelists and Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, German idealist philosophers of the West. In fact, it is Philosophy in contrast to the sacred scriptures of Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism in traditional Eastern philosophy. With this purpose, "Existentialism is a new name for an ancient method" states Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan p. 443. It claims that our existence as unique and individuals in concrete situations is not just personalized task and cannot be grasped in theories; and that it cannot be obscured from the world while it aims to attain self-fulfilment in our lives.

Satre strongly asserted that, "existentialism is not a disciplined philosophical system but a label for revolts in diverse guises against traditional philosophy." p.1 Sartre's finds origins of philosophy in classical philosophers.

For Plato, Philosophy is search for Essence, because Essence is immutable. Spinoza sought access to an eternal life which is Beatitude. Generally speaking, the philosopher has wished to rise above realm of becoming and find the truth universal and eternal.

Jean-Paul Sartre in *The Philosophy of Existentialism- Selected Essays*, p.2.

Since Hegel is believed to the last philosopher on existentialism solely by reasoning. He insisted on understanding the world with reason, one's thoughts and feelings have sense and they are directly proportional to one's existence. To understand totality of oneself. He opines that

"Our thoughts and feelings have meaning solely because each thought

and each feeling is bound to our personality, which itself has meaning only because it takes place in a history and a state, at a specific epoch in the evolution of the universal idea. To understand anything that happens in our inner life of the universal idea. To understand anything that happens in our inner life we must go to the totality which is our self, thence to the larger totality which is the human species, and finally to the totality which is the absolute idea. p.11

Existentialism is enlivening but alarming philosophical journey that drives, realities of life—freedom, alienation, anxiety, despair, absurdity and authenticity into the marrow of human existence and essence. It dismantles the conventions and convictions established by philosophers like Aristotle that "essence precedes existence." p.22. which means that individual's existence in this world is destined by God, the Supreme Authority, who designs schedule of individuals the time one is born till death.

Its fundamental pursuit raises complex eternal questions that encounter the purpose of one's existence, lies rooted in aspirations of existentialist individual affirms Kierkegaard. He defines existential individual as one who has "Infinite relationship with himself and has an infinite interest in himself and his destiny." p.2. one becomes what one wants to be only when one applies the idea and passionate thought, which stimulates the existent individual as a driving force with sustained effort. Passion or vigour that leads individual to the infinite is what Kierkegaard calls "the passion of freedom." Freedom of choice and decision have significance in philosophy of Kierkegaard as each decision signifies risk for the individual who is filled and enclosed by uncertainty. Significance of individual faith and subjectivity are considered forerunners of new radiance in history of Existentialism. Existentialists grip on to the thought that people have liberty to decide. Hence, they decide what they mean, make choices and handle factors that confront them. They are self-creating, as they design their essence and hold responsible for their actions or judgements. They are masters of their own destiny and fulfil their lives. An individual creates his existence with clarity and intensity from his profound emotional, personal experience.

Succeeding Nietzsche, it tiled the path to radical thinking in values and confronted the rudiments of ethics, ideologies and meaning with revolutionary proclamation that "God is dead." p.2, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* p.108. in *The Gay Science*. While Simon de Beauvoir who, with her rebellion on patriarchy in her seminal work *The Second Sex*, said, "One is not born, but rather

becomes, a woman.” p. 283 as key thought in the concept of feminism reaffirming and referring to sex—biological characters—and gender roles, identity and behaviour. Albert Camus focus on absurdity of human state and bringing an upsurge against it in Existentialism to flourishing worldwide.

Franz Kafka’s attention is on alienation and brutalization of individuals. Ravages of World War II resulted in existential crisis played pivotal role in rise of radiating existential ideas. Humanities existential crisis constitutes loss, absurdity and alienation—demanded new philosophical jargon that underlined personal meaning over universal order. Speciality of existential philosophy does not answer eternal questions of life but kindles the flames the blaze of thought. Its concepts echo depths of rising wonder. It walks along tradition asking what it means to be free to choose, to carry the weight of meaning in a world that offers nothing along the winding path of specific ideas that take shape not as doctrines but as companions of thought. Sartre’s “Existence precedes Essence” is the first ideology existentialism which implies that man is not born with a predefined purpose or essence. Through his choices, and responsibilities, he outlines the purpose with which he entered the world denying the classical views. Man exists, confronts challenges, exerts himself, and rises to assert his identity. This theory is concerned with finding meaning and self through free will and personal responsibility.

Decisions decide destiny is Sartre’s another great doctrine “Man is nothing else but what he makes of himself.” P.22. Modern existentialists believe that an individual’s essence is not prescribed in advance by God or parents but designed by one’s choice created from freedom and responsibility. Theoretically, this stance indicates that one’s route or destination is not predetermined by destiny or by divine will, it unveils through decisions, verdicts, ideologies and specific dutiful responsibility of an individual. Unlike conventional philosophies, whose quest for fixed truth depend on Divine decree to state meaning of one’s fate. Existentialism as a theory is self-permeable or absorbent philosophy focusses on original experience without stress of autonomy, the strife of uncertainty, and prerequisite to create one’s meaning in the world that does not suggest anything to anyone by default.

Freedom and Responsibility are duo which go as accompaniment with one another for every individual from the time of birth. Individuals take the responsibility for one’s own significance and live life ardently and interpreting at one’s choice despite hinderances and distractions like anxiety, despair, fret, absurdity, choice and death. Freedom is intimate with radical responsibility. One is responsible for negotiating with meaning and consequences of one’s life without intervention of God, nature or society. Satre says: “Man is condemned to be free; because once thrown into the world, he is responsible for everything he does” p. 3.

‘Angst and Anxiety’ are existential concepts that mirror the confrontation of man with liberty, choice and loss of inherent essence. Soren Kierkegaard differentiates anxiety from fret which is specific object and subjective: anxiety arises from endless possibilities of awareness to infuses despair, liberating from the burden of responsibilities and hence it is more abstract. Martin Heidegger strengthens anxiety in Being and Time, as oblivion or emptiness in routine as anxiety or angst. This conflict permits authenticity by challenging personal announcements against societal interferences for authentic living, as anxiety arouses anxiety vital for self-creation and human freedom, insisting responsibility and authenticity.

Existential thinkers feel life to be absurd because it is bereft on inherited meaning. Camus in his seminal work *The Myth of Sisyphus* illustrates human existence to be meaningless struggle still, promotes to pursue absurdity as a rebellious act against incomprehensive services to explore meaninglessness of freedom and existence. Sisyphus negates God and infers that the universe without Controller is not futile nor sterile. In tiny measure accepting absurdity shows embracing meaninglessness and vain efforts also there is fulfilment because labour yields

happiness and never goes vain. Though ironical Camus finds meaning even in absurdity in this apathetic universe.

Authenticity is embracing freedom and responsibility to create meaning in social roles. Sartre believes when one exists in the world one is incompetent to escape selecting a route and reap its consequences. Heidegger strengthens 'authenticity' from confrontation even with mortality. Kierkegaard add "the relation that relates itself to itself" as a dynamic scuffle between desire and wisdom. One choses to craft one's essence through acts of self-awareness. Heidegger's Dasein, meaning "being there" draws attentions towards authentic existence. It is unique human way of being, defined not by essence but by existence in the world, engaged with entities.

One's identity is formed from one's self-awareness and understanding one's essence. "Hell is other people" Sartre illustrated that the look of others externalizes and objectifies a person from subjective front and it interrupts internal freedom fixing one's identity. According to Sartre's principle, Existence precedes essence," affirms that individuality is not declared in advance; at the same time. it is created our of one's fancy and any intervention by others creates conflicts and hinderance, when a person asserts one's actions and identity through subjectivity. Look of others definitions, restricts or sets limits and yet, paradoxically, sustains one's existence in reality.

Meaning and absurdity of one's life begins with questioning. Suicide according to Camus is a decision to endure life or to end it confirms the meaning of absurdity. One's combat with the absurd is the tension for yearning for clarity from the silence of absurdity. Suicide is thus a revolt against meaninglessness and encounter life's despair refusing to a compromise with life and confrontation with death describing the sickness of the soul and also according to Kierkegaard, spiritual decadence failing to lead an authentic life. Death is no longer realizing one's possibilities of life and lack of responsibility to create meaning and combat circumstances without fret but affirmation to coexist in diverse conflicting demands with fierce rebellious personal experiences.

Facticity in Existentialism, symbol of concrete truth based on which a human is trapped eternally and that a person is left with no choice than to encounter but it is not imprisonment but becomes a platform for freedom. Sartre describes it as "background of which human freedom exists and is limited" p.555 in *Being and Nothingness*. Facticity includes body, birthplace, language, past actions and mortality. Sartre insists on "what is important is not what is made of man, but what he makes of what is made of him" p.4.

'Leap of faith' another existential concept according to Soren Kierkegaard and Friedrich Nietzxsche, are fore runners of existentialism who are deeply concerned with Christian faith. For them subjectivity is truth. hence, the truth lies in subjectivity everything generates from experience of aguish. Faith is inward passion and personal commitment "Life must be understood only backwards, but it must be lived forwards" p. 306, affirms the lines *From The Sickness unto Death*, which is the essence inferred at the end of the novel.

Dostoevsky paved the path for subjectivity opposing the norms and rules of the system, to dispel myth of heroism. Kierkegaard criticizes the Hegelian thought advocating importance to individual faith and subjectivity is observed as a herald of fresh ideal in the tale of existentialism. Heidegger's Dasein, or Kierkegaard's idea of individual, underlines conflicts and confrontation between ethical, aesthetic and religious faith. Religious dogmas indorsed giving priority to quintessence on human reality. Nietzsche, influenced by Marxism and atheism in Existentialism proposes the readers to face mortality with respect and pride calling it Nihilism. He champions imaginative artistic power when philosophy begins enquiring the values and objectivity of truth in socio cultural and moral settings. Existentialism remains vague and ambiguous and unexplored without Heidegger's emphasis on Dasein emphasising importance of authenticity

and relevant of time in existence. Jaspers evaluates ideas proposed in all branches of philosophy thought inadequate to address human attributes or traits.

Conclusion

Existential thoughts unfold human life and reveal uncertainty, freedom and responsibility towards one's actions. Individuals cannot escape the burden of choice, even under oppressive or disastrous circumstances. The characters and situation illustrate people confront alienation, suffering, moral ambiguity which searching for the purpose of life in absurd world. As the existence does not answer but emphasizes the need to face reality. Through struggles individuals assert identity, through decision they take. The work demonstrates existential crisis for people who demand self- recognition and ethical awareness. The paper unfolds the struggle to fragile yet resilient nature of human existence.

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